

EXPLORING FLUENCY AND COMPREHENSION AS BASIS FOR INTERACTIVE REMEDIAL READING TOOL (IRRT)

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the levels of fluency and comprehension among grade four learners in the District of Calinog II, Province of Iloilo, during the School Year 2023-2024, and explores the relationship between language use, technology utilization, reading fluency, and comprehension. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, the study aims to inform evidence-based practices and pedagogical strategies for enhancing language learning outcomes in the digital age. A sample of grade four students from ten elementary schools within the district participated in the study, with data collected using a two-part research instrument. The first part assessed the frequency of English language use and technology accessibility, while the second part utilized an adapted Philippine Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) assessment tool to evaluate reading fluency and comprehension. Data analysis involved descriptive and inferential statistics, including Percentage and Frequency Count, Rank, Mean, Standard Deviation, the Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis Test, and Spearman's rho analyses. Findings revealed that overall reading fluency and comprehension were at instructional levels among the respondents. While occasional English language users demonstrated independent-level fluency, all groups displayed instructional-level fluency regardless of technological accessibility. The preferred technological learning materials were computing and mobile devices. Significant differences were observed in reading fluency and comprehension based on frequency of English language use and technological utilization, highlighting the impact of these factors on literacy development. Moreover, a positive and significant relationship between fluency and comprehension was identified, underscoring the importance of fluency in enhancing reading comprehension skills. Based on the study results, an Interactive Remedial Reading Tool, named Comprehensive Literacy Development, is proposed to address identified literacy needs.

Keywords: *exploring fluency, comprehension, Interactive Remedial Reading Tool (IRRT)*

INTRODUCTION

In the pursuit of enhancing literacy skills among grade four learners, the exploration of fluency and comprehension as the foundational elements for an Interactive Remedial Reading Tool (IRRT) becomes paramount. Fluency, the ability to read with accuracy, speed, and expression, and comprehension, the capacity to understand and interpret text, are essential components of proficient reading. Recognizing the significance of these skills, this study aims to investigate their role in developing an effective IRRT tailored to the specific needs of learners in the Schools District of Calinog II, Province of Iloilo, during the School Year 2023-2024.

Despite numerous interventions and initiatives aimed at improving reading proficiency, there remains a gap in addressing the individual needs and learning styles of students, particularly in the context of remedial reading programs. Existing tools often overlook the interactive and personalized aspects necessary for effective remediation. Moreover, while fluency and comprehension are recognized as fundamental to reading success, there is a dearth of research focusing on their integration into interactive remedial tools tailored to the unique challenges faced by grade four learners. Thus, this study seeks to fill this gap by examining the potential of an IRRT that prioritizes fluency and comprehension within the context of the Schools District of Calinog II, Province of Iloilo.

In today's rapidly evolving educational landscape, the integration of technology into language learning environment has emerged as a promising avenue for enhancing students' proficiency in English. The role of technology in education has become increasingly prominent, with educators exploring innovative ways to integrate digital tools into various aspects of teaching and learning. Among the areas where technology shows significant promise is literacy instruction, where researchers have identified its potential to enhance students' reading fluency and comprehension skills. In the scheme / system framework of education, literacy serves as a cornerstone for academic success and lifelong learning. Fluency and proficiency in reading comprehension lays the foundation for effective communication, critical thinking, and acquired knowledge.

The importance of literacy development has long been recognized in educational research and practice. Numerous studies have highlighted the significance of reading fluency and comprehension in academic achievement and overall literacy proficiency. Reading fluency refers to the ability to read text accurately, smoothly, and with expression, while reading comprehension involves understanding and interpreting the meaning of written text.

Despite their recognized importance, many students find it challenging to achieve proficiency in fluency and comprehension. Factors like limited exposure to language,

inadequate reading practice, and poor access to educational resources can hinder literacy development. Furthermore, technological advancements present both new obstacles and opportunities in literacy education, necessitating innovative approaches to meet changing educational needs.

The critical role of reading fluency and comprehension in academic success underscores the urgent need for effective interventions to help struggling learners. An Interactive Remedial Reading Tool (IRRT) could be a promising solution to these issues by offering personalized, engaging, and accessible learning experiences.

By utilizing technology, the IRRT could provide interactive exercises, adaptive learning pathways, and immediate feedback to address specific needs and foster skill development. Additionally, incorporating language learning programs into the tool could increase the frequency of English usage, thus enhancing outcomes in reading fluency and comprehension. In this study, the researcher aim to explore the relationship between reading fluency, comprehension, and the effectiveness of the IRRT as a remedial intervention. By examining how the tool impacts learners' fluency and comprehension skills, the researcher seek to contribute to the development of evidence-based practices in literacy education and support the diverse learning needs of students. Through this research, aspire to empower educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers with insights and tools to foster literacy excellence and educational equity.

The interconnectedness and interdependence of reading fluency and comprehension are fundamental aspects of literacy development. Understanding their interplay is crucial for unlocking the complex mental and linguistic processes of reading.

The motivation for this study originated from the ongoing difficulties in reading fluency and comprehension among fourth-grade students in Calinog II District, as highlighted by the 2023 PHIL-IRI results. This ongoing struggle raised concerns about the broader implications for academic performance and overall learning outcomes.

The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines has several legal foundations for conducting the Phil-IRI reading assessment among learners. These stem from the "Every Child A Reader Program" (ECARP) initiative, established through DepEd Memorandum No. 402, s. 2004 (Department of Education, 2004).

The ECARP program aims to ensure every Filipino child becomes a proficient reader and writer at their grade level. It centers on the core principle of personalized learning, aiming to ensure every Filipino child becomes a proficient reader and writer at their grade level. Further strengthening ECARP, DepEd Administrative Order No. 324, s. 2012 (Department of Education, 2012) mandates the use of assessment tools like the Phil-IRI. Additionally, DepEd Order No. 23, s. 2018 (Department of Education, 2018) outlines specific guidelines for administering the Phil-IRI assessment for Grades 3-6 in public elementary schools nationwide. By utilizing the Phil-IRI assessments as diagnostic tools, teachers gain valuable insights into individual student needs (Department of Education, 2018). This empowers them to tailor their instruction and interventions,

fostering an inclusive learning environment where each child receives the targeted support necessary to achieve their full potential in reading development (Department of Education, 2012).

Research Questions

This study aims to test and analyzed respondents' reading fluency and comprehension, as well as their interactions.

The study seeks answers to the following questions:

1. What is the frequency of using the English language in your daily life among respondents?
2. What is the preferred classroom technological learning materials used among respondents?
3. What is the level of reading fluency among the respondents as a whole and when grouped according to frequency of English language use and technological utilization?
4. What is the level of reading comprehension among the respondents as a whole and when grouped according to frequency of English language use and technological utilization?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of respondents' reading fluency when grouped according to frequency of English language use and technological utilization?
6. Is there a significant difference in the level of respondents' reading comprehension when grouped according to frequency of English language use and technological utilization?
7. Is there a significant relationship between reading fluency and reading comprehension?
8. What output can be developed based on the study's findings?

METHODOLOGY

This study aimed to provide valuable insights into the level of fluency and comprehension among the respondents and the relationship between variables. By examining the interplay between language use, technology utilization, reading fluency, and comprehension, the research aimed to inform evidence-based practices and pedagogical strategies for enhancing language learning outcomes in the digital age.

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing quantitative methods to examine the relationship between English language use, technology utilization, reading fluency, and reading comprehension among 200 grade four learners in the District of Calinog II, Schools Division, Province of Iloilo during the School Year 2023-2024. The sample comprised grade four students from ten elementary schools within the district, with sample size determination based on the Gay formula (1976) to ensure adequate representation.

The research instrument consisted of two parts: Part one assessed the frequency of English language use and technology accessibility. While part two utilized an adapted Philippine Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) assessment tool to evaluate reading fluency and comprehension, featuring 20 comprehension items and individual fluency assessments based on a rubric.

Data collection involved administering questionnaires personally by the researcher among the selected grade four students in elementary schools in the district of Calinog II. Subsequently, collected data were meticulously checked, tallied, and processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses were employed to explore relationships between variables and draw meaningful conclusions. Data analysis involved descriptive and inferential statistics, including Percentage and Frequency Count, Rank, Mean, Standard Deviation, the Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis Test, and Spearman's rho analyses.

RESULTS

Table 1. *Frequency of Using English Language in Daily Life*

Category	F	%
Rarely	25	12.5
Seldom	136	68
Occasionally	39	19.5
Total	200	100

Table 2. *Preferred Type of Technological Learning Materials*

Category	Mean	rank
Display and Presentation Devices	2.21	2
Computing and Mobile Devices	3.71	1
Audio System	1.52	3

Table 3. *The Level of Reading Fluency among the Respondents as a Whole and when Grouped according to Frequency of English Language and Technological Utilization.*

Category	Mean	Description
Entire Group	96.64	Instructional
Frequency of English Language		
Rarely	95.84	Instructional

Seldom	96.65	Instructional
Occasionally	97.13	Independent
Level of Technological Utilization		
Not accessible	96.50	Instructional
Limited accessible	96.53	Instructional
Adequately accessible	96.77	Instructional

Table 4. *The Level of Reading Comprehension among the Respondents as a Whole and when grouped according to frequency of English Language and Technological Utilization.*

Category	Mean	Description
Entire Group	80.26	Instructional
Frequency of English Language		
Rarely	78.84	Instructional
Seldom	79.71	Instructional
Occasionally	83.10	Independent
Level of Technological Utilization		
Not accessible	66.00	Instructional
Limited accessible	79.12	Instructional
Adequately accessible	82.17	Independent

Scale:

Mean	Description
80.00 – 100.00	Independent
59.00 – 79.99	Instructional
58.99 and below	Frustration

Table 5. *The Kruskal-Wallis Test Result for the difference in the level of Reading Fluency among the Respondents when grouped according to frequency of English Language and Technological Utilization*

Compared Groups	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
<i>Frequency of English language</i>			16.199**	2	.000
Rarely	25	66.96			
Seldom	136	100.25			
Occasionally	39	122.88			
<i>Technological utilization.</i>			2.657	2	.265
Not accessible	4	90.00			
limited accessible	104	94.95			
Adequately accessible	92	107.23			
Total	200				

*p<0.001, significant at 0.001 alpha

Table 6. *Posterior (Mann Whitney U) test Result for the Pair wise comparisons of the Means in the Frequency of English language*

Compared Groups	Z	Sig
Rarely - Seldom	2.940**	.003
Rarely – Occasionally	3.631***	.000
Seldom- Occasionally	2.388*	.017

***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p< 0.05 alpha ;

Table 7. *The Kruskal-Wallis Test Result for the difference in the level of comprehension among the respondents when grouped according to frequency of English language and Technological Utilization.*

Compared Groups	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
<i>Frequency of English language</i>			17.851**	2	.000
Rarely	25	87.74			
Seldom	136	93.62			
Occasionally	39	132.68			
<i>Technological utilization.</i>			18.566**	2	.000
Not accessible	4	22.00			
limited accessible	104	90.90			

Adequately accessible	92	114.76
Total	200	

*p<0.001, significant at 0.001 alpha

Table 8. *Posterior (Mann Whitney U) test Result for the Pair wise comparisons of the Means in the Frequency of English Language*

Compared Groups	Z	Sig
Rarely - Seldom	.534	.593
Rarely – Occasionally	3.210*	.001
Seldom- Occasionally	4.040**	.000

***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p< 0.05 alpha ;

Table 9. *Posterior (Mann Whitney U) test Result for the Pair wise comparisons of the Means in the technological utilization*

Compared Groups	Z	Sig
Not accessible- Limited accessible	2.680*	.007
Not accessible- Adequate accessible	3.236*	.001
Limited accessible - Adequate accessible	3.158**	.002

*p<0.01, significant at 0.01 alpha;*p<0.05, significant at 0.05 alpha

Table 10. *The Spearman’s Correlation Matrix for the relationship between level of fluency and reading comprehension*

Correlated	r	Sig
level of fluency and reading comprehension	.288***	0.000

P*** < .001 , significant at .001 alpha

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the frequency of using the English language in daily life among respondents. Among the respondents, 25 individuals, equivalent to 12.5% of the total sample, reported rarely utilizing the English language in their daily activities. The majority of respondents, 136 individuals, or 68% response, seldom utilizes the English language in their daily lives. Additionally, 39 respondents, representing 19.5% of the sample, occasionally utilized the English language in their day-to-day activities. Among the respondents, 25 individuals, equivalent to 12.5% of the total sample, reported rarely utilizing the English language in their daily activities. In contrast, the majority of respondents, 136 individuals, or 68% of the sample response, seldom utilize the English language in their daily lives. Additionally, 39 respondents, representing 19.5% of the sample, occasionally utilized the English language in their day-to-day activities.

Table 2 shows the preferred type of technological learning materials utilized by the respondents, as well as their corresponding mean ranks. Among the categories, computing and mobile devices emerge as the most preferred types, with a mean rank of 3.7. The display and presentation devices, with a mean rank of 2.21, placed second in the ranking. In contrast, audio systems exhibit the lowest mean rank of 1.52.

Table 3 shows that the level reading fluency among the respondents as a whole (M= 96.64; SD = .135) and when grouped according to frequency of English language respondents who rarely (M= 95.84; SD = 1.14) and seldom (M= 96.65; SD = 1.25) utilizing the English language in their daily activities exhibit “Instructional” level of reading fluency. However, occasionally (M= 97.13; SD = 1.59) utilizing the English language in their daily activities exhibit “Independent”.

Table 5 shows that the level reading comprehension among the respondents as a whole (M= 80.26; SD = 7.59) and when grouped according to frequency of English language respondents who rarely (M=78.84; SD = 8.25) and seldom (M= 79.71; SD = 7.73) utilizing the English language in their daily activities both within the “Instructional” range. However, occasionally (M = 83.10; SD = 6.01) utilizing the English language in their daily activities exhibits an “independent” level of comprehension.

The difference in the level of reading fluency among the respondents when grouped according to frequency of English language and Technological utilization in table 6. The Kruskal - Wallis Test result revealed significant difference in the level of reading fluency among the respondents when grouped according to frequency of English language ($\chi^2(2)=16.199$; $p= .000$). The p value is less than .05. The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in level of reading fluency among the respondents when grouped according to frequency of English language was rejected.

The Mann-Whitney U test was conducted to analyze the differences in reading fluency levels among groups categorized by their frequency of English language usage. The results revealed significant disparities in reading fluency between several pairs of groups. Specifically, individuals who rarely used English exhibited notably different reading fluency levels compared to those who seldom used the language, with a Z value of 2.940 ($p = .003$). Similarly, significant differences were observed between individuals who rarely used English and those who occasionally used it, as indicated by a Z value of 3.631 ($p = .000$). Additionally, a statistically significant distinction in reading fluency levels emerged between individuals who seldom used English and those who occasionally used it, with a Z value of 2.388 ($p = .017$).

These findings underscore the impact of language usage frequency on reading fluency, suggesting that varying degrees of exposure to English may influence individuals' proficiency in reading comprehension and fluency. Such insights can inform educational strategies tailored to accommodate diverse language backgrounds and usage patterns, ultimately promoting more equitable learning outcomes. These findings align with research by Cunningham and Stanovich (1991), who emphasize the critical role of language exposure in literacy development. Additionally, studies by Scarborough (2001)

support the idea that frequency of language use correlates with reading proficiency, corroborating the significant differences observed in this study.

The difference in the level of reading comprehension among the respondents when grouped according to frequency of English language and Technological utilization in table 6. The Kruskal - Wallis Test result revealed significant difference in the level of reading fluency among the respondents when grouped according to frequency of English language ($\chi^2 (2) = 17.851$; $p = .000$) and technological utilization ($\chi^2 (2) = 18.566$; $p = .000$). The p values are less than .05. The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in level of reading fluency among the respondents when grouped according to frequency of English language and technological utilization was rejected.

The result of the Spearman's rho in table 10 shows positive significant relationship between level of fluency and reading comprehension ($r = .288$; $p = 0.000$). The p value is less than .05. It means that the respondents' level of fluency is associated with or related to their reading comprehension skills.

These findings are supported by previous research. For example, studies by Stanovich and Cunningham (1992) emphasize the positive relationship between fluency and reading comprehension, suggesting that fluent readers are better able to understand and process written texts. Additionally, research by Perfetti and Hart (2001) corroborates the idea that fluency plays a crucial role in comprehension, supporting the positive relationship found in this study.

The findings of the study suggest important implications for theoretical frameworks concerning language learning and literacy development. Specifically, the results underscore the significance of English language use frequency in shaping reading fluency and comprehension levels, emphasizing the crucial role of language exposure in literacy acquisition. This aligns with theoretical perspectives such as the Input Hypothesis proposed by Krashen (1985), which posits that language acquisition occurs through exposure to comprehensible input. Additionally, the study highlights the secondary role of technological accessibility in literacy development compared to language use frequency, challenging assumptions about the primacy of technology in enhancing reading skills. These implications contribute to a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between language factors and technological influences on literacy outcomes within theoretical frameworks of language acquisition and literacy development.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the different conclusions were drawn:

1. Reading fluency levels among respondents are influenced by both frequency of English language use and technological accessibility. While higher English language use frequency correlates with higher fluency levels, technological accessibility alone may not significantly impact fluency. However, occasional English language users demonstrated

independent-level fluency, indicating a potential need for tailored interventions to support their reading development.

2. Computing and mobile devices are the most preferred technological learning materials among respondents, followed by display and presentation devices, while audio systems are the least preferred. These preferences highlight the importance of considering learner preferences when integrating technology into educational environments.

3. The study demonstrates that reading fluency levels are influenced by frequency of English language use, with occasional users exhibiting higher fluency levels compared to those who rarely or seldom use English. This highlights the importance of language exposure and practice in developing reading proficiency, with frequent engagement potentially leading to more fluent reading skills. Interestingly, the study also indicates that technological accessibility does not independently influence fluency levels, as all groups, regardless of accessibility, demonstrate instructional-level fluency.

4. The reading comprehension levels are influenced by frequency of English language use, with occasional users exhibiting higher comprehension levels compared to those who rarely or seldom use English. Moreover, technological accessibility appears to play a role in comprehension outcomes, as respondents with adequate accessibility demonstrate independent-level comprehension.

5. The reading fluency levels significantly differ based on frequency of English language use, emphasizing the role of language exposure in literacy development. However, technological utilization does not significantly influence reading fluency levels, suggesting that other factors may play a more prominent role in fluency outcomes.

6. The study demonstrates significant differences in reading comprehension levels among respondents based on both frequency of English language use and technological utilization. These findings emphasize the multifaceted nature of literacy development and underscore the importance of addressing both language and technological factors in educational contexts.

7. The study demonstrates a significant positive relationship between fluency and reading comprehension among respondents. These findings underscore the critical role of fluency in supporting comprehension skills and suggest that efforts to enhance fluency may contribute to improved reading outcomes.

8. The development of an Interactive Remedial Reading Tool should embrace a comprehensive approach to literacy development, encompassing both language and technological dimensions. By incorporating language-focused activities alongside modules that enhance technological literacy skills, such as digital reading comprehension exercises, online research tasks, and critical evaluation of digital resources, the tool ensures that learners receive holistic support in their literacy journey. This approach acknowledges the interconnectedness of language proficiency and digital literacy skills,

recognizing their importance for success in navigating today's digital age. Through this integrated approach, the tool empowers learners to develop the necessary competencies to thrive academically and professionally in an increasingly digital and information-rich environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher offered the following recommendations.

1. Include implementing targeted language learning programs to increase English language use frequency among respondents, particularly for those categorized as occasional users. Additionally, educational initiatives should aim to provide equitable access to technological resources while recognizing that fluency development may require additional support beyond technological access alone.

2. Educators and curriculum developers should prioritize the integration of computing and mobile devices into instructional practices to align with learner preferences and potentially enhance learning outcomes. Additionally, further research could explore the specific features and functionalities of preferred technological materials to inform the design and implementation of more effective educational technologies.

3. Educational practitioners should prioritize interventions aimed at promoting regular English language use among learners to enhance reading fluency. Additionally, efforts to improve technological accessibility should be complemented by language-focused interventions to ensure comprehensive literacy development. Further research is warranted to explore the nuanced interactions between language use, technological access, and reading fluency in diverse educational contexts.

4. Educational practitioners should prioritize interventions aimed at promoting regular English language use among learners to enhance comprehension proficiency. Additionally, efforts to improve technological accessibility should be implemented to provide equitable learning opportunities and support independent-level comprehension. Further research is warranted to explore the complex interactions between language use, technological access, and reading comprehension in diverse educational contexts.

5. Educators and policymakers should prioritize interventions aimed at increasing English language exposure among learners to enhance reading fluency. Additionally, while technology can be a valuable tool in education, its integration should be complemented with strategies targeting language development to maximize literacy outcomes. Further research could explore the nuanced interactions between language use, technological utilization, and reading fluency to inform more targeted interventions in educational settings.

6. Educational practitioners should design comprehensive literacy programs that integrate opportunities for regular English language engagement and effective utilization

of technology. Additionally, efforts should be made to ensure equitable access to language and technological resources to support literacy development for all learners. Further research could explore the specific mechanisms through which language exposure and technological utilization influence reading comprehension to inform more targeted interventions.

7. Educators should incorporate activities and strategies that promote fluency development into their instructional practices. Additionally, ongoing assessment of fluency levels can help identify students in need of targeted intervention and support. Furthermore, further research could explore the specific mechanisms through which fluency influences reading comprehension to inform more effective instructional approaches.

8. To effectively address the multifaceted needs of learners, educators and developers should prioritize the creation of an Interactive Remedial Reading Tool that embraces a comprehensive approach to literacy development. This tool should not only focus on language proficiency but also incorporate modules designed to enhance technological literacy skills. By providing a diverse range of activities, such as digital reading comprehension exercises, online research tasks, and critical evaluation of digital resources, learners can develop both their language and digital literacy competencies simultaneously. Additionally, the tool should be designed to adapt to individual learning needs, offering personalized support and intervention to maximize learning outcomes. Through this integrated approach, the Interactive Remedial Reading Tool can empower learners with the skills and knowledge necessary for success in today's digital age.

9. Future researchers should explore the efficacy of blended learning approaches that combine targeted language learning programs with technological interventions to further enhance literacy outcomes and address the diverse needs of learners in various educational contexts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to participation, parents or legal guardians of the minor respondents were provided with clear and comprehensive information about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. They gave their informed consent for their child to participate, ensuring they understood their rights and the voluntary nature of participation. Measures were in place to protect the confidentiality of the participants' personal information and responses. Data collected were anonymized or coded to ensure that individual responses could not be traced back to specific participants. Confidentiality was maintained throughout data collection, analysis, and reporting. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and participants were free to withdraw from the study at any time without consequences. Coercion or undue pressure to participate was avoided, and participants were made aware of their right to withdraw without penalty. Researcher took steps to ensure that the study benefitted participants and minimized any potential harm. This included ensuring that the study did not cause any physical or psychological harm to the participants. Researchers were prepared to offer support or referrals to appropriate

resources if any distress or harm arose during or after participation. The study respected the cultural norms, values, and beliefs of the participants and their communities. Researchers were sensitive to cultural differences and ensured that the study design, materials, and procedures were culturally appropriate and respectful. Measures were implemented to ensure the security and integrity of the data collected. This included securely storing physical and electronic data, limiting access to authorized personnel only, and protecting against unauthorized access, loss, or theft of data. Researcher conducted the study with honesty, integrity, and transparency, adhering to ethical guidelines and standards of professional conduct. Any conflicts of interest or potential biases were disclosed, and research findings were reported accurately and impartially.

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